

АНАЛІЗ СТАНУ МІКРОЦИРКУЛЯТОРНОГО РУСЛА ЩЕЛЕПНО-ЛИЦЕВОЇ ДІЛЯНКИ ШЛЯХОМ ВИКОРИСТАННЯ ЛАЗЕРНОЇ ДОПЛЕПРОВСЬКОЇ ФЛОУМЕТРІЇ

ANALYSIS OF CONDITION MICROCIRCULATORY LEVEL OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL AREA BY USING LASER DOPPLER FLOWMETRY

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Introduction: Laser doppler flowmetry allows you to measure microcirculation in human and animal tissues. This approach was first used in the 1980s and continues to be used because it is non-invasive and easy to use after a period of study. The principle of laser doppler flowmetry is based on the interaction of light with tissue on the principle of the Doppler effect on laser radiation.

The aim of the study: is to identify the possibility of using Doppler laser flowmetry in dentistry.

Materials and methods: The principle of the technique is that the fiber optic probe of the analyzer provides delivery of probing radiation from the laser to the research area and transportation to the photodetectors of the radiation reflected from the tissue, contains three monofilaments oriented when the measuring perpendicular to the surface.

When interacting with tissue in the reflected signal there is a component due to the reflection of moving erythrocytes, proportional to the speed of movement (Doppler effect). The amplitude of signals in the device is formed from all erythrocytes in the area of probing, moving at different speeds and differently quantitatively distributed in arterioles, capillaries, venules and arteriovenular anastomoses.

Research results: Registration of the speed of the microcirculatory tract was performed in the projection of anatomical formations: mental hole, infraorbital hole, central incisor hole, the base of the interdental papilla, and the apex of the root.

Conclusions: As a result of the study, the expediency of using laser Doppler flowmetry to assess the state of the microvasculature of the maxillofacial area was revealed, since this technique can be used in the vast majority of dental areas due to its non-invasiveness and adaptive versatility.

Also, based on this analysis of changes in the microvasculature, the technique allows monitoring both the stages of the inflammatory process and the stages of regeneration in soft tissues.

Literature:

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